

Some New Complexes of Indium(III) Salts with Acid Hydrazides

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The complexes of the type $[\text{In}(\text{LH})_2]\text{X}_2$, $[\text{In}(\text{LH})_2\text{X}]$, $[\text{In}(\text{LH})_2\text{X}]_2\text{X}$, $[\text{In}(\text{LH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ and $[\text{In}(\text{L})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [where LH—the neutral molecules of benzoylhydrazine (BH, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHNH}_2$), salicyloylhydrazine (SH, $o\text{-OH-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHNH}_2$), paramethoxybenzoylhydrazine (PMBH, $p\text{-MeO-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHNH}_2$) and paranitrobenzoylhydrazine (PNBH, $p\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHNH}_2$), and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}] have been prepared by reacting indium(III) salts with the suitable ligand and characterised by elemental analysis, infrared spectra and molar conductivity measurements.

Since the discovery of the antitubercular activity of acid hydrazides, many workers¹⁻⁹ have studied the coordination chemistry of these ligands.

These ligands contain different coordination centers and form two kinds of complexes. In neutral or slightly acidic medium, they act as neutral mono- or bi-dentate ligands forming cationic complexes, while in basic medium they act as monobasic bidentate forming neutral complexes^{8,10,11}. As monodentate, they coordinate through either of their donor atoms^{7,8,12,13}.

In this paper the results of our investigation on the synthesis and characterisation of some new complexes of indium(III) with aroylhydrazines in both neutral and basic medium, are reported.

Experimental

Preparation of ligands: The ligands, benzoyl-, salicyoyl-, *p*-methoxybenzoyl- and *p*-nitrobenzoylhydrazines were generally prepared by the reaction of hydrazine hydrate with the corresponding ester according to the standard procedures¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

Preparation of complexes: Several complexes of different types were isolated by the reaction of indium (III) salts with the ligands. In neutral medium, the reaction was carried out in alcoholic (ethanolic or methanolic) solutions in ~1 : 3 metal to ligand ratio (always 1 g metal salt was used with the corresponding amount of the suitable ligand). The reaction mixture was refluxed for ~1 h and then allowed to cool. In the basic medium, potassium hydroxide solution was added slowly to the mixture until complete precipitation of the complexes at pH 7-8.5. The isolated compound were filtered off, washed several times with cold alcohol followed by recrystallisation from ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The complexes containing sulphate groups were prepared by fusion of 2 g indium(III) sulphate with

1.6 g benzoylhydrazine or 1.8 g salicyloylhydrazine (1 : 3 metal to ligand stoichiometry) at temperature slightly above the melting point of the ligands. The reacting mixture was cooled, followed by several times washing with ethanol, and dried in a vacuum desiccator to yield the products, benzoylhydrazine complex (1.55 g, 78%) and of salicyloylhydrazine complex (1.4 g, 66.6%).

TABLE I—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED ANALYTICAL DATA
Compound Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)

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	C	H	N	X*	In
In(BH) ₂ Cl ₂	39.86 (40.12)	4.03 (3.82)	13.13 (13.37)	16.51 (16.72)	18.27 (18.31)
In(BH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	35.56 (35.53)	3.22 (3.39)	17.51 (17.77)	—	16.08 (16.22)
[In(BH) ₂ SO ₄] ₂ SO ₄	31.75 (31.64)	3.05 (3.02)	10.42 (10.55)	9.41 (9.04)	21.40 (21.66)
In(SH) ₂ Cl ₂	37.01 (37.22)	3.63 (3.55)	12.21 (12.41)	16.11 (15.66)	17.30 (16.98)
In(SH) ₂ Br ₂	26.21 (26.50)	2.61 (2.42)	8.18 (8.49)	36.11 (36.41)	17.35 (17.45)
[In(SH) ₂ SO ₄] ₂ SO ₄	29.63 (29.84)	2.95 (2.84)	10.14 (9.95)	8.52 (8.35)	20.62 (20.43)
In(SH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	33.22 (33.29)	3.31 (3.31)	17.56 (17.77)	—	15.34 (15.18)
In(PMBH) ₂ Cl ₂	40.23 (40.06)	4.21 (4.17)	11.51 (11.68)	14.68 (14.74)	16.25 (15.98)
In(PMBH) ₂ Br ₂	28.18 (27.95)	3.07 (2.91)	8.40 (8.15)	35.21 (34.93)	16.44 (16.74)
In(PNBH) ₂ Cl ₂	33.30 (32.98)	2.86 (2.75)	16.58 (16.49)	14.06 (13.87)	15.2 (15.04)
In(PNBH) ₂ Br ₂	28.19 (28.06)	2.46 (2.34)	14.16 (14.03)	26.82 (26.77)	12.67 (12.80)
In(BH) ₂ ·2H ₂ O**	45.21 (45.32)	4.71 (4.50)	14.93 (15.11)	—	20.35 (20.68)
In(SH) ₂ ·2H ₂ O**	42.16 (41.93)	3.62 (3.66)	14.21 (13.98)	—	19.31 (19.12)
In(PMBH) ₂ ·2H ₂ O**	44.72 (44.58)	4.91 (4.80)	13.18 (13.00)	—	17.65 (17.80)
In(PNBH) ₂ ·2H ₂ O**	36.62 (36.47)	3.31 (3.18)	18.45 (18.23)	—	16.46 (16.64)

* X = Sulphur/ chlorine/ bromine.

** The same complexes were obtained by reaction of corresponding ligand with any of indium salts in alkaline medium or with indium hydroxide.

Elemental analysis: The isolated complexes were analysed for carbon, nitrogen, hydrogen, halogen, sulphur and indium by Alfred Bernhardt (West Germany) microanalyser. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Physical measurements: Molar conductivity of the complexes in acetonitrile and dimethylformamide (DMF) at concentration $10^{-3}M$ were taken on an electrolytic conductivity measuring set model MC-1.

Ir spectra (KBr, nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

In continuation of our work^{13, 17, 19}, we prepared a number of complexes of indium(III) in both neutral and alkaline media.

In the preparation of the complexes in alcoholic solution always 1 : 3 complexes separated out even when excess of the ligands was used, while 1 : 2 complexes were obtained for indium bromide and indium sulphate. Analytical data (Table 1) show that the ligands form different types of complexes depending on the medium and the method of preparation. In neutral solution cationic and neutral complexes were obtained. In alkaline medium or by reaction with indium hydroxide, the ligands loses one proton to form deprotonated neutral complexes having 1 : 3 metal to ligand ratio, and usually one complex was separated out by the reactions of the different indium salts or indium hydroxide with the same ligand.

All the complexes are insoluble in water and most of the organic solvents, but they are slightly soluble in ethanol, dimethylformamide and acetonitrile. The cationic complexes melt in the range 95-230°, while the neutral complexes generally do not melt below 250° (Table 2). The neutral complexes are non-electrolyte. However, the molar conductivities of cationic complexes lying in the ranges 190-220, 140-150 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ in dimethylformamide and 110-130, 80-100 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ in ethanol, indicate 1 : 3 and 1 : 2 electrolytes (Table 2).

TABLE 2 - MELTING POINTS, AND MOLAR CONDUCTIVITIES ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) AT 25° OF $10^{-3} M$ SOLUTIONS IN DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE (DMF) AND ETHANOL

Compound	Λ_m (DMF)	Λ_m (ethanol)	M.p. °C
In(BH) ₂ Cl ₂	220	128	92-94
In(BH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	194	116	237
In(SH) ₂ Cl ₂	218	121	126-128
In(SH) ₂ Br ₂	139	98	147-150
In(SH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	202	121	-
In(PMBH) ₂ Cl ₂	211	124	146-148
In(PMBH) ₂ Br ₂	146	112	136-138
In(PNBH) ₂ Cl ₂	12	6	172-174
In(PNBH) ₂ Br ₂	22	18	198-200
In(BH) ₂ .2H ₂ O	8	20	-
In(SH) ₂ .2H ₂ O	16	14	-
In(PMBH) ₂ .2H ₂ O	24	8	-
In(PNBH) ₂ .2H ₂ O	23	15	-

Infrared spectral data indicate that coordination in the complexes takes place in three different ways. (i) For complexes formed with benzoyl-, salicyloyl- and paramethoxybenzoylhydrazine in neutral solution, a negative shift of the order 15-28 cm^{-1} was observed for C=O stretching vibrations and a decrease of about 20-35 cm^{-1} in NH₂ bending frequencies. In addition the other NH₂ deformation vibrations located in the free ligands²² at 950-1350 cm^{-1} are shifted to lower frequencies by the same order. While the positions of the bands due to NCO and OH deformation vibrations remain almost unchanged upon complex formation. These negative shift of C=O and NH₂ bands can be regarded as an evidence of coordination through both carbonyl oxygen and terminal hydrazide nitrogen atom. (ii) For complexes formed by reaction with *p*-nitrobenzoylhydrazine in neutral solution, the spectra of these complexes show negative shift of the order 25-40 cm^{-1} only in NH₂ bending vibrations, which indicate that the ligand coordinate only through the amino-nitrogen atom¹³.

For complexes formed in alkaline solution also two different ways of coordination are indicated. (i) With the exception of salicyloylhydrazine complexes, in the spectra of the complexes formed with the other ligands, C=O stretching bands were absent. Instead two medium intensity bands appeared at 1320-1370 and 1600-1610 cm^{-1} , which are due to the stretching vibrations of C=O single and C=N double bonds, respectively (because of the conversion of the ligands to the enolic form in alkaline medium). The NH₂ deformation vibrations show a decrease of the order 20-35 cm^{-1} . Thus, coordination occurs through the enolic oxygen and the amino-nitrogen atoms. (ii) For SH complexes in the basic medium, the spectra indicate coordination through both imido-nitrogen (secondary amide nitrogen atom) and phenolic oxygen atoms, since the bands due to NCO deformation and OH stretching vibrations, present at 793 and 3500 cm^{-1} , respectively in the spectrum of the free ligand, were absent in the spectra of the complexes. This may support the above suggestion and indicate complexes with six-member ring structure.

In the spectra of the complexes, In(SH)₂Br₂, In(PMBH)₂Br₂, In(PNBH)₂Cl₂ and In(PNBH)₂Br₂, two bands in the low frequency region (260-295 cm^{-1}) are assigned to In-Cl and In-Br stretching vibrations, keeping in view their molar conductance.

Two complexes containing sulphate, [In(BH)₂SO₄]₂SO₄ and [In(SH)₂SO₄]₂SO₄ were prepared by fusing indium sulphate with the ligands in 1 : 3 molar ratio. The spectral bands at 1180, 1095, 1010 and 940 cm^{-1} are assigned to S-O stretching vibrations for the bridging bidentate sulphate²³. In all the complexes, indium ion is six-coordinated with octahedral structure.

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